

A Study Determining the Etiology of Thrombocytosis and Analyze Various Platelet Parameters in ChildrenArvind Kumar Yadav¹, Manish Ranjan², Kripa Nath Mishra³¹Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India³Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was aims to determine the etiology of thrombocytosis and analyze various platelet parameters in children.**Methods:** This was a prospective observational study carried out in the Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga medical College and Hospital. All children of age group 1–14 years of age attending pediatrics outdoors and indoors of DMCH were included in the study. A total of 272 children presented with thrombocytosis.**Results:** Age group ranged from 1 to 14 years out of which majority were in 1–2 years age group (45%). 70% children had mild thrombocytosis whereas moderate and severe thrombocytosis was seen in 24% and 3%, respectively. Etiology was secondary or reactive in 99.5% cases whereas only one case of primary thrombocytosis was encountered. Primary or clonal thrombocytosis was seen in one case of Philadelphia positive pediatric CML. No cases of ET were encountered. Etiological spectrum of secondary thrombocytosis was extremely varied. Infection was the most common cause for secondary thrombocytosis, with the highest number attributed to respiratory tract infections alone. For analyzing the association of platelet indices with the severity of thrombocytosis, the cases were grouped into three categories (mild, moderate, severe + extreme) and mean value, standard deviation and P value was calculated. On analysis, an inverse relationship between the platelet indices and the degree of thrombocytosis was observed. With increasing platelet counts, there was a decrease in MPV which had a significant negative correlation ($P < 0.05$). Mean PDW of children with mild and moderate thrombocytosis was 10.96 fl and 10.26 fl, respectively.**Conclusion:** Thrombocytosis in children is predominantly secondary and primary (clonal) thrombocytosis is extremely rare. The most common etiology of secondary thrombocytosis in children is infections and is a transient phenomenon with no major clinical implications. However, if no secondary cause is found for increased platelet count or if it persists even after treating the primary cause, a search for underlying primary thrombocytosis should be done.**Keywords:** Platelet indices, primary, secondary, thrombocytosisThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Thrombocytosis refers to platelet count $>4,00,000/\mu\text{L}$ in the peripheral blood. [1] With the widespread use of electronic cell counters and the subsequent availability of a platelet count as part of a routine blood count, thrombocytosis is more often observed as an unexpected finding. Thus, an elevated platelet count has become an important clinical problem for differential diagnosis of various pathological and physiological processes. [2,3]

Thrombocytosis is classified according to its origin into primary and secondary forms. Primary (clonal) thrombocytosis is a myeloproliferative disorder,

caused by abnormal and uncontrolled expansion of haematopoietic cells, which is likely to be complicated by thromboembolism. [2] Secondary (or reactive) thrombocytosis is due to a variety of underlying conditions like infection, inflammation, iron deficiency, tissue damage, hemolysis, severe exercise, malignancy, hyposplenism, and other causes of an acute phase response. [4] It is sometimes difficult to differentiate between both categories on clinical ground alone. Once thrombocytosis is identified and confirmed by peripheral smear, the diagnostic evaluation turns to

determine whether the process is reactive or clonal in nature. An important initial step in this is familiarity with the underlying causes of thrombocytosis.

Thrombocytosis is classified according to its origin into primary and secondary forms. Primary (clonal) thrombocytosis is a myeloproliferative disorder, caused by abnormal and uncontrolled expansion of haematopoietic cells, which is likely to be complicated by thromboembolism. [5] Secondary (or reactive) thrombocytosis is due to a variety of underlying conditions like infection, inflammation, iron deficiency, tissue damage, hemolysis, severe exercise, malignancy, hyposplenism, and other causes of an acute phase response. [6] In older adults an elevated platelet count can signify an underlying hematological disease, in children in almost every case the elevated platelet count is due to another medical condition, such as acute infection, chronic inflammation, collagen vascular and renal diseases, Langerhan's cell histiocytosis, iron deficiency, hemolytic anemia, and Kawasaki disease (KD). [7,8] Drugs are another less frequent cause of secondary thrombocytosis in children. [9,10]

The aim of the present study was aims to determine the etiology of thrombocytosis and analyze various platelet parameters in children.

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective observational study carried out in the Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India for 12 months. All children of age group 1–14 years of age attending pediatrics and pediatric super specialty outdoors and indoors were included in the study. A total of 272 children presented with

thrombocytosis. All cases with incomplete workup and repeat hemograms of same patients were excluded from the study. Routine Complete hemogram was done using 2 ml of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid blood in 6 part differential hematology Autoanalyzer (XN-1000) and cases which showed thrombocytosis were reviewed on peripheral smear. Once it was confirmed on smear, case history, presenting signs and symptoms, history and drug history were recorded. The complete blood counts parameters such as hemoglobin, red cell indices, and platelet indices (platelet distribution width [PDW], mean platelet volume [MPV], platelet large cell ratio [P-LCR], and plateletcrit) were noted. Other relevant biochemical parameters such as C-reactive protein, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, serum iron profile, blood culture, and urine culture were also recorded as per the clinical indications in each case. Thrombocytosis was graded into mild ($>500 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$ – $7 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$), moderate ($>7 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$ – $9 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$), severe ($>900 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$), and extreme ($>1000 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$) as per Dame and Sutor⁷ Etiology was determined after analyzing clinical along with relevant laboratory parameters and cases were categorized into subgroups accordingly. All the repeat hemograms of same patients were excluded from the study. The study was approved by the institutional ethical committee. Informed consent was taken from the parents of all patients included in the study.

Statistical analysis was performed on SPSS version 20. Mean, standard deviation and P value were calculated. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Grades of thrombocytosis with age groups

Grades of thrombocytosis	1-2 years, n	2-6 years, n	6-10 years, n	10-14 years, n	Total, n (%)
Mild	59	30	21	30	140 (70)
Moderate	28	10	8	2	48 (24)
Severe	0	5	1	0	6 (3)
Extreme	3	2	0	1	6 (3)
Total	90	47	30	33	200

Age group ranged from 1 to 14 years out of which majority were in 1–2 years age group (45%). 70% children had mild thrombocytosis whereas moderate and severe thrombocytosis was seen in 24% and 3%, respectively.

Table 2: Etiology of thrombocytosis

	n (%)
Primary (n=1) CML	1 (100)
Reactive (n=199)	27
Iron deficiency anemia	20
Infection and anemia	80
Infection alone	14
	36

Urinary tract infection	18
Respiratory tract infection	43
Gastrointestinal infection	64
Bacteremia	16
CNS infection	30
Hemoglobinopathies	20
Drugs	3
Surgery	
Trauma/burn	

Etiology was secondary or reactive in 99.5% cases whereas only one case of primary thrombocytosis was encountered. Primary or clonal thrombocytosis was seen in one case of Philadelphia positive pediatric CML. No cases of ET were encountered.

Etiological spectrum of secondary thrombocytosis was extremely varied. Infection was the most common cause for secondary thrombocytosis, with the highest number attributed to respiratory tract infections alone.

Table 3: Correlation of platelet indices (platelet distribution width, mean platelet volume, P-large acell ratio)

Grades of thrombocytosis	PDW Mean SD	MPV Mean SD	P-LCR Mean SD
Mild	10.96 ±1.4	9.92 ±0.8	22.88 ±6.4
Moderate	10.26 ±1.5	9.53 ±1.0	21.68 ±6.2
Severe+extreme	10.05 ±2.7	9.32 ±0.8	20.6 ±7.3
Total	10.78 ±1.4	9.82 ±0.8	22.92 ±6.4
<i>P</i>	0.007	0.012	0.003

with Severity of thrombocytosis
For analyzing the association of platelet indices with the severity of thrombocytosis, the cases were grouped into three categories (mild, moderate, severe + extreme) and mean value, standard deviation and P value was calculated. On analysis, an inverse relationship between the platelet indices and the degree of thrombocytosis was observed. With increasing platelet counts, there was a decrease in MPV which had a significant negative correlation ($P < 0.05$). Mean PDW of children with mild and moderate thrombocytosis was 10.96 fl and 10.26 fl, respectively.

Discussion

Extreme thrombocytosis (platelets $>1,000,000/\mu\text{L}$) is uncommon, occurring in less than 2% of children [11], but may be more common in critically ill children. [12] Thrombocytosis is classified according to its origin into primary and secondary forms. Primary (clonal) thrombocytosis is a myeloproliferative disorder, caused by abnormal and uncontrolled expansion of haematopoietic cells, which is likely to be complicated by thromboembolism. [5] Once thrombocytosis is identified and confirmed by peripheral smear, the diagnostic evaluation turns to determine whether the process is reactive or clonal in nature. An important initial step in this is familiarity with the underlying causes of thrombocytosis. There have been few prospective studies on the clinical circumstances surrounding paediatric thrombocytosis and

evaluation of platelet indices (mean platelet volume, platelet distribution width, and plateletcrit) in presence of thrombocytosis.

Age group ranged from 1 to 14 years out of which majority were in 1–2 years age group (45%). 70% children had mild thrombocytosis whereas moderate and severe thrombocytosis was seen in 24% and 3%, respectively. The frequency of reactive thrombocytosis in childhood is age-dependent with the highest incidence up to 2 years of age. [12] Literature review shows mild increase in platelet counts up to $7,00,000/\mu\text{L}$ in 72%–86% cases, moderate and severe thrombocytosis in 6%–8% and 2%–3% of children, respectively. [7] The incidence of newly diagnosed primary thrombocytosis in children is about 1 per 10 million, about 60 times lower than adults. [6]

Etiology was secondary or reactive in 99.5% cases whereas only one case of primary thrombocytosis was encountered. Primary or clonal thrombocytosis was seen in one case of Philadelphia positive pediatric CML. No cases of ET were encountered. Etiological spectrum of secondary thrombocytosis was extremely varied. Infection was the most common cause for secondary thrombocytosis, with the highest number attributed to respiratory tract infections alone. A study by Dame and Sutor concluded that the most common cause for reactive thrombocytosis during childhood is (acute or chronic) bacterial or viral infections. [7] In this group, respiratory tract infection is most common

followed by gastrointestinal and urinary tract infection. [13,14] For analyzing the association of platelet indices with the severity of thrombocytosis, the cases were grouped into three categories (mild, moderate, severe + extreme) and mean value, standard deviation and P value was calculated.

On analysis, an inverse relationship between the platelet indices and the degree of thrombocytosis was observed. With increasing platelet counts, there was a decrease in MPV which had a significant negative correlation ($P < 0.05$). Mean PDW of children with mild and moderate thrombocytosis was 10.96 fl and 10.26 fl, respectively. Drug-induced thrombocytosis following intake of corticosteroids and chemotherapeutic agents like vincristine was seen in a relatively higher number of cases in our center. Most of these cases were of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia on vincristine or steroid therapy who presented with reactive thrombocytosis on multiple occasions. It has been suggested that vincristine decreases platelet utilization resulting in increased platelet life span and also increases its marrow production. [15] This high number can be attributed to the fact that this hospital is a referral center for hemato-oncology cases. Two cases of ITP on steroids also presented with rebound thrombocytosis during treatment. Corticosteroids can lead to transient thrombocytosis, by releasing stored platelets from the spleen into the blood circulation. [16] In ITP, megakaryopoiesis is accelerated as a response to immune-mediated destruction of platelets. Sometimes, during therapy, compensatory platelet overproduction in the phase of decreased or normalized platelet destruction may lead to thrombocytosis. Three cases with ITP, who developed rebound thrombocytosis following steroid treatment was reported by Yohannan et al¹¹ IDA alone and with associated concurrent infections comprised 14.1% and 10.3% of secondary thrombocytosis, respectively.

Conclusion

Thrombocytosis in children is predominantly secondary and primary (clonal) thrombocytosis is extremely rare. The most common etiology of secondary thrombocytosis in children is infections and is a transient phenomenon with no major clinical implications. However, if no secondary cause is found for increased platelet count or if it persists even after treating the primary cause, a search for underlying primary thrombocytosis should be done.

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